

Load-bearing capacity of lockbolt systems made from carbon steel subjected to combined tension and shear loading

Alexander Holch^{*,a}, Ralf Glienke^b, Maik Dörre^a, Knuth-Michael Henkel^c

^aFraunhofer Institute for Large Structures in Production Engineering (IGP), Rostock, Germany
alexander.holch@igp.fraunhofer.de, maik.doerre@igp.fraunhofer.de

^bUniversity of Applied Science in Wismar, Dept. of Engineering, Wismar, Germany
ralf.glienke@hs-wismar.de

^cUniversity of Rostock, Dept. of Mechanical and Naval Engineering, Rostock, Germany
knuth.henkel@uni-rostock.de

ABSTRACT

For bearing type connections subjected to combined tension and shear loading (category A+D, EN 1993-1-8), the interaction verification according to Eurocode 3 is required. The use of so-called lockbolt systems is an alternative to conventional bolted connections in steel structures. The linear interaction approach according to technical bulletin DVS/EFB 3435-2 is a conservative assumption, due to the lack of knowledge about the behaviour of lockbolts under combined loading. In more than 900 tests, the interaction resistance of tensile test pieces, fully and partially threaded bolts and lockbolt systems was examined, and additional numerical analyses were carried out. Based on a statistical evaluation, a new design proposal for the interaction verification of lockbolts is pointed out.

Keywords: lockbolt systems, interaction loading, design approach, reliability analysis

1 INTRODUCTION

The lockbolt technology (Fig. 1) is a mechanical joining technology that enables connections with load-bearing behaviour comparable to that of bolted connections. A lockbolt system consists of the bolt and the softer collar made from carbon steel, stainless steel, or aluminum. Lockbolts made from carbon steel can correspond to property classes according to ISO 898-1 (1). The assembly of lockbolts is a torsion-free preloading by elongating the bolt, while the softer collar material is formed into the grooves of the bolt. Due to this plastic deformation, lockbolt systems are secured against self-loosening. The torsion-free preloading results to a low scattering of the initial preload. There are different types of lockbolts categorised according to DVS-EFB 3435-1 (2), with type A and type C being the most commonly used. Type A is a lockbolt with shank in the shear plane and plane-parallel lock grooves. The pin tail at the end of the bolt is required for the assembly tool to apply the installation force. For type A lockbolts the pin tail is designed as tear-off part with a predetermined breaking point. Lockbolts type C have helical grooves almost up to the head. The short pin tail is designed without breaking point. More detailed information about the technology of lockbolt systems can be found in DVS-EFB 3435-1 (2) and (3).

In contrast to the design principle of tensile loaded bolted connections (failure in the free loaded bolt thread), the tensile failure mechanism of lockbolts is characterised by collar stripping. When subjected to single shear loading, bolts and lockbolts fail due to shear fracture in the shear plane.

The design of connections with lockbolt systems is carried out according to DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4), also referring to (5). For connections in steel construction, the design rules are based on those for bolted connections according to Eurocode 3 (EN 1993-1-8 (6)). Due to the lack of knowledge about the load-bearing behaviour under combined tension and shear loading, the linear interaction model was agreed as a conservative assumption for lockbolt systems.

Both under single tension load and under single shear loading, lockbolts have a higher load capacity than fully threaded bolts with the same property class and nominal size because of the larger tensile stress area. Due to the conservative interaction model, the higher individual load-bearing capacities do not come into effect for combined tension and shear loading.

Within the framework of a publicly funded research project (7), experimental and numerical studies were carried out on lockbolt systems from carbon steel to address the lack of knowledge of combined tension and shear resistance and to develop an approach for the interaction verification of lockbolt systems. This paper focuses on the results and the statistical evaluation of experimental investigations.

Fig. 1 Lockbolt system type A (left) and type C (right) with and without pre-determined break neck (2)

2 APPROACHES FOR INTERACTION VERIFICATION

The relevant European interaction approaches for bolted connections from standards and current research are summarised in Table 1. The interaction of tension and shear utilisation is described by linear, nonlinear, and quadratic approaches. In contrast to EN/prEN 1993-1-8 (6; 8) and Može (9) in the interaction verification of (10; 11; 12; 13), the tension resistance of the cross-section areas A_s or A in shear plane is considered. Nevertheless, the tension load acting at the tensile stress area A_s outside of the shear plane is to verify. In consequence, the interaction load-bearing capacity is still limited by the tension resistance of the tensile stress area outside of the shear plane. For the case of shank cross-section in the shear plane, this is visualised by the horizontal cutting of the interaction model, see Fig. 4, left. The interaction models are shown in the interaction diagrams (Fig. 4).

Table 1. Design approaches for interaction verification of carbon-steel bolting assemblies

EN 1993-1-8 (6) and prEN 1993-1-8 (8)	MOŽE (9)
$\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}} + \frac{F_{t,Ed}}{1.4 \cdot F_{t,Rd}} \leq 1$ (1) $F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s	$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.5} + \left(\frac{0.9 \cdot F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,Rd}}\right)^{1.5} \leq 1$ (2) $F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s
DIN 18800-1 (10) from KNOBLOCH/SCHMIDT (11)	STRANGHÖNER/ABRAHAM (13)
$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,Rd}}\right)^2 \leq 1$ (3) $F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s or A	$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} \leq 1$ (4) $F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s for threaded part in the shear plane
RENNER/LANGE (12)	
$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.5} + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,Rd}}\right)^{1.5} \leq 1$ (6) $F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s or A	$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{1.25 \cdot F_{t,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} \leq 1$ (5) $1.25 \cdot F_{t,Rd}$ with A_s for unthreaded part in the shear plane

A – gross-section of the bolt, A_s – tensile stress area of the bolt

$F_{v,Ed}$ – design shear force, $F_{v,Rd}$ – design shear resistance, $F_{t,Ed}$ – design tension force, $F_{t,Rd}$ – design tension resistance

The design rules of lockbolt systems according to DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4) are based on EN 1993-1-8 (6), see Table 2. The interaction verification is carried out by the linear interaction of the tension utilisation for collar stripping and the shear utilisation of the bolt. In order to provide a simple verification, the tensile load-bearing capacity is limited to exceeding the yield strength of the lockbolt reduced by 10% despite the failure of the collar. The determination of the shear resistance is based on EN 1993-1-8 (6) with a modified shear coefficient.

Table 2. Design rules for lockbolt systems made from carbon steel

DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4)

Tensile resistance		Shear resistance		Interaction resistance	
$F_{t,Rd} = \frac{k_2 \cdot f_y \cdot A_S}{1.1 \cdot \gamma_{M,LB}}$ (7)	$k_2 = 1.0$ $\gamma_{M,LB} = 1.1$	$F_{v,Rd} = \frac{\alpha_v \cdot f_{ub} \cdot A}{\gamma_{M2}}$ (8)	PC 5.8, 8.8, 10.9: $\alpha_v = 0.55$	$\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}} + \frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,Rd}} \leq 1$ (9)	
<p>A – gross-section of the lockbolt, A_S – tensile stress area of the lockbolt, α_v – shear coefficient $\gamma_{M,LB}$ – partial factor of collar stripping, γ_{M2} – partial factor of bolt resistance $F_{v,Ed}$ – design shear force, $F_{v,Rd}$ – design shear resistance, $F_{t,Ed}$ – design tension force, $F_{t,Rd}$ – design tension resistance</p>					

3 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

3.1 Test setup and test program

To conduct experimental investigations into the load-bearing behaviour under combined tension and shear loading, a testing device was developed based on (14). According to the findings of DÖRRE et al. (15), single shearing is investigated. The thickness of the test inserts is equal, so that the shear plane is in the centre of the clamping length. The ratio of simultaneous tension and shear loading is set by the angle of load application φ , which can be adjusted in increments of 7.5°.

Fig. 2 Device for testing under combined tension and shear loading

For different fasteners, a total of $n = 5..7$ tests, depending on the scattering, are carried out for each angle of load application. The tests were conducted in a stroke-controlled testing mode at the test machine Z400E (ZWICK/ROELL) until the fasteners failed into two parts. Table 3 and Table 4 display the test program. Bolting assemblies and lockbolt systems of different diameter d and property classes (PC) were tested, see Table 3 and Table 4.

Table 3. Test program of bolts and tensile test pieces

bolt standard	d in mm	PC	SC	bolt standard	d in mm	PC	SC
ISO 4017 (16)	8.0	5.6	ub	ISO 4014 (17)	8.0	5.6	ub
	8.0	8.8	ub		8.0	8.8	ub
	16.0	8.8	ub		16	8.8	ub
	16.0	10.9	ub		16.0	10.9	ub
	16.0	8.8	hdg		16.0	8.8	hdg
Tensile test piece (DIN 50125 (18), 1.7225)	8.0	-	-	EN 14399-4 (19)	16.0	10.9	hdg

property class (PC), surface condition (SC): uncoated black (ub), hot dip galvanised (hdg)

The structure of the test program is chosen in order to investigate the interaction behaviour of specimens with increasing design complexity. At first, the interaction resistance of a bolt typical quenched and tempered steel 42CrMo4+QT (1.7225) is examined on round bars (tensile test piece form B (18)). The aim is to determine the interaction resistance without the influences of notch strengthening, cross-section changes and changing failure modes. In comparison, fully threaded bolts according to ISO 4017 (16) of different diameters and property classes are investigated. Also,

investigations were carried out on hexagon head bolts according to ISO 4014 (17) and HV-bolts according to EN 14399-4 (19) with the shank positioned in the shear plane. The aim is, to observe the interaction behaviour on specimens with a changing failure location for tension and shear loading. The main part of the test program are the studies on lockbolt systems of type A and type C. In total, 374 tests on bolting assemblies and 572 tests on lockbolt systems were carried out.

Table 4. Test program and geometric and mechanical properties of lockbolt systems

Manufacturer, product name	Designation of test series	Type	Part in shear plane	d in mm	PC	SC	$A_{obs,mean}$ in mm ²	V_{Aobs}	$f_{ub,obs,mean}$ in N/mm ²	$V_{f_{ub}}$
Howmet, Bobtail	H-BT_6.4_8.8	C	shank	6.4	8.8	zf	33.3	0.40 %	1028.0	1.23 %
	H-BT_7.9_8.8	C	shank	7.9	8.8	eg	51.2	0.24 %	1106.3	2.67 %
	H-BT_9.6_8.8	C	shank	9.6	8.8	zf	74.6	0.21 %	1074.9	0.89 %
	H-BT_12.0_10.9	C	grooves	12.0	10.9	zf	99.5 ^a	0.64 %	1116.5	3.14 %
	H-BT_16.0_10.9	C	grooves	16.0	10.9	zf	175.2 ^a	0.52 %	1181.0 ^b	2.01 %
Howmet, C120L	H-C120L_9.6_8.8	A	shank	9.6	8.8	eg	73.4	0.16 %	1037.4	1.78 %
Howmet, C50L	H-C50L_12.7_8.8	A	shank	12.7	8.8	eg	125.1	0.14 %	962.9	0.56 %
Titgemeyer, Delta-Bolt	T-DB_9.6_5.6	A	shank	9.6	5.6	eg	73.7	0.26 %	821.7	2.45 %
	T-DB_9.6_8.8	A	shank	9.6	8.8	ub	73.1	0.22 %	1000.6	3.36 %
Goebel, Standard-LB	G-StS_9.6_5.6	A	shank	9.6	8.8	eg	74.0	0.14 %	835.7	1.92 %

surface condition (SC): zinc-flake coated (zf), uncoated black (ub), electro-galvanised (eg)
^a tensile stress area A_S for lockbolt systems according to DVS-EFB 3435-2
^b material strength converted from hardness value

3.2 Characterisation of test samples

In preparation of the test evaluation and the statistical evaluation, the geometric and mechanical properties were determined for the lockbolt systems. The relevant geometric properties are the diameters of the shank and grooves of the bolt in order to define the load-transmitting shear cross-section A , measured for each specimen. The diameters were measured with a calibrated calliper or measurement microscope. The material strength is determined by tensile tests according to DVS-EFB 3435-1 (2) based on ISO 898-1 (1) on turned tensile test pieces taken from the bolt. Due to the geometry of lockbolt H-BT_16.0_10.9, it was not possible to design a tensile test piece that met the requirements for the specimen geometry of DIN 50125 (18). Hence the material strength was determined by hardness tests according to DVS-EFB 3435-1 (2) based on ISO 898-1 (1). Vickers hardness tests were carried out according to ISO 6507-1 (20) and the conversation of hardening in material strength follows ISO 18265 (21). A summary of the properties and the coefficients of variation V_X is given in Table 4.

3.3 Procedure of test evaluation

The result of a single test is the maximum endured load and the failure mechanism. The endured tension and shear load components are evaluated by the loading angle φ . Regarding the latest design approaches, the position of the shear plane is considered in the evaluation of the test results. The test results are presented in the so-called interaction diagram in form of the endured load component utilisations and are confronted with the interaction models from Table 1 and Table 2.

The shear resistance $F_{v,max}$ is directly determined as the test result from shear tests ($\varphi = 90^\circ$), Eq. (10). The tension resistance of the shear cross-section $F_{t,max}$ is determined regarding to the specimen geometry and the tensile failure mechanism. For tensile test pieces and fully threaded bolts, the tension resistance $F_{t,max}$ is also directly determined as the test result from tension tests ($\varphi = 0^\circ$), Eq. (11). For partially threaded bolts, the tension resistance in the shear plane is calculated under considering the ratio of the cross-sectional areas, Eq. (12). The modified stress area A_S^* takes the so-called transition effect (22) into account. This effect describes an increasing tensile load-bearing capacity with reducing the distance between nut and thread run-out due to a decreasing relief notch

effect and is obtained by finite element analyses, see chapter 4. For lockbolt systems, the tension resistance in the shear plane is calculated with the shear cross-sectional area and the ultimate strength from tensile material tests, Eq. (13).

Determination of shear load utilisation:
$$F_v/F_{v,max} = F_{mean} \cdot \sin \varphi / F_{90^\circ,mean} \quad (10)$$

Determination of tensile load utilisation:

For tensile test pieces and fully threaded bolts:
$$F_t/F_{t,max} = F_{mean} \cdot \cos \varphi / F_{0^\circ,mean} \quad (11)$$

For partially threaded bolts with shank in shear plane:
$$F_t/F_{t,max} = (F_{mean} \cdot \cos \varphi / F_{0^\circ,mean}) \cdot A_s^* / A \quad (12)$$

For lockbolt systems:
$$F_t/F_{t,max} = (F_{mean} \cdot \cos \varphi) / (f_{u,obs} \cdot A) \quad (13)$$

Only test results with failure in the shear cross-section are allowed to be compared with interaction models. Failure outside of the shear plane results only from the tensile load component and is not ensured by the interaction verification for combined tension and shear loading.

3.4 Test results and evaluation

Exemplary failure modes for tensile test pieces, fully and partially threaded bolts are shown in Fig. 3 and the evaluation of the endured partial utilisations is presented in Fig. 4, left. For tensile test pieces and fully threaded bolts, the test results settle in a nonlinear, arched manner, on the uncertain side of the quadratic interaction model. Tensile test pieces fail under single tension load ($\varphi = 0^\circ$) with the fracture occurring between the thread ends in the waist. As expected, the bolts fail in the free loaded thread, in accordance with the design principle. When a superimposed shear force is introduced, both the tensile test pieces and the fully threaded bolts fail in the shear plane.

The observed failure mechanism for partially threaded bolts indicates that failure in the free loaded thread does not solely occur under single tension load, as depicted in Fig. 3, right. Even with superimposed shear load at loading angles up to 15° , the characteristic tension failure takes place outside the shear plane. For larger load application angles, the failure location changes and shifts to the bolt shank at the location of the shear plane.

For small loading angles, the larger cross-sectional area in the shear plane allows to absorb the superimposed tension and shear loads. Only the tension load component leads to failure in the free loaded thread outside the shear plane within the smaller tensile stress area.

By considering the tension resistance of the shear cross-sectional area A , the utilisations for large tension load components, causing failure in the free loaded thread, are arranged horizontally, aligned with the ratio of tensile resistances of stress area to shank cross-section. For loading angles above 15° , the failure location changes to the shank cross-section within the shear plane, and the test results also settle in an arc below the quadratic interaction model, see Fig. 4 left. Therefore, the linear interaction models are not suitable for a reliably describing the course of the result points.

The main finding of the result evaluation of tensile test pieces, fully and partially threaded bolts is the arrangement in a common scatter band for interaction failure in the shear plane. Regarding lockbolt systems, this indicates the potential for a satisfying description of the interaction behaviour by considering the tension resistance of the shear cross-section, independent from different failure modes.

Fig. 3 Failure modes of tensile test pieces (left), fully threaded bolts (centre) and partially threaded bolts (right)

Fig. 4 Interaction diagrams for bolts (left) and lockbolt systems (right)

Fig. 5 Failure modes of lockbolt systems

The results for lockbolt systems are given in Fig. 4 (right). For single tension load ($\varphi = 0^\circ$), but also with superimposed shear load up to $\varphi = 37.5^\circ$, the characteristic failure observed is collar stripping, as shown in Fig. 5. When considering the tension resistance of the shear cross-section, the test results associated to collar stripping are arranged horizontally in the interaction diagram. In contrast to partially threaded bolts, the resistance to tensile failure and the tensile resistance of the bolt cross-section are in an individual ratio for each lockbolt system. This is caused by the not standardised geometries and collar strengths as well as the influence of assembly tooling. Due to the higher material strength of the bolt compared to the tension resistance for collar stripping, a larger shear load component can be endured in the shear plane in addition to the tension load. Therefore, even at loading angles of up to 37.5° (T-DB_9.6_5.6), the lockbolt system failed due to collar stripping. For results with failure in the shear plane, the test points are arranged together as an arch-shape below the quadratic interaction model, similar to the arrangement for tensile test pieces and bolts.

The current interaction approach for lockbolt systems describes the interaction resistance by the linear interaction between the resistance to collar stripping and the shear resistance. It becomes visible, that the load-bearing behaviour, represented by the arrangement of the filled markers, is not sufficient described by this formulation.

4 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATIONS

The focus of the numerical investigations is to get a detailed view on the interaction load-bearing behaviour of tensile test pieces, fully and partially threaded bolts and lockbolt systems with the same material properties, as this was not possible in the experimental investigations.

At first, a model of the tensile test piece was created. The thread ends and the nuts were neglected and assumed as one body. Due to the stiffness of the test device, only the test inserts were considered

and the symmetry in z-direction [A] is also taken into account. Linear-elastic material properties are defined for the test inserts, while for the tensile test piece the experimental obtained flow curve is assigned. The contacts between the inserts and the nuts are assumed as bonded (B). Frictional contact conditions ($\mu = 0.1$) are defined between the specimen surface and the inserts through-hole (F). The load is applied by remote displacements in the bearing points of the test device, see Fig. 2. A local coordinate system is used, which is rotated around global z-axis so that the local x-axis corresponds to the load direction. The remote displacement [C] of one test insert is fixed ($u_x = u_y = 0$ mm, $rot_z = 0^\circ$). The remote displacement [B] of the other insert is applied in local x-direction, while local y-direction is fixed ($u_y = 0$ mm) and local z-rotation is free as in the experimental setup. Due to the large deformations, fine meshing is required in the area of the shear plane. Also, a nonlinear adaptive region is defined for remeshing, which requires tetrahedral elements with quadratic basis function (TET10). The model and the boundary conditions are summarised in Fig. 6, left. Furthermore, models of partially and threaded bolts as well as lockbolts are created in the same manner, using the flow curve of the tensile test piece. For partially threaded bolts, the model was simplified by considering the tensile stress area. For fully threaded bolts symmetry cannot be considered.

Fig. 6 Overview of FEA model (left) and interaction diagram (right)

The comparison of the interaction load-bearing capacities of the tensile tests piece from experiment and simulation shows an agreement to over 97.8 %, which validates the FE model. The endured utilisations from the different models are evaluated following Eq. (8) to (11). For the results of partially threaded bolts and lockbolts related to tension failure mechanism, the horizontal arrangement in the interaction diagram is observed, see Fig. 6, right. The results related to failure in the shear cross-section show a sufficient agreement. This confirms the independence of the interaction load-bearing behaviour from the shape of the fastener (shank, thread, or grooves in shear plane) as well as from different tension and shear failure locations.

Due to the same diameter and the same material properties, the tension load capacity of the tensile test piece corresponds to that of the bolt shank. When comparing the tensile test piece and the free loaded thread, a discrepancy was detected in the ratio of tension resistances and the ratio of cross-sectional areas due to the transition effect. For this reason, additional FE analyses with detailed modelled thread and thread run-out were carried out on the basis on geometrical measurements on each type of tested partially threaded bolt. As result, the modified tensile stress area A_S^* was determined for each partially threaded bolt for the investigated clamping length l_c , see Table 5.

The studies of Renner/Lange (12) and Stranghöner/Abraham (13) indicate a less interaction behaviour of partially threaded bolts compared to fully threaded bolts. In contrast, considering the transition effect in the evaluation of test results leads to a common placement of the results from tensile test pieces, fully and partially threaded bolts, see Fig. 4, left.

Table 5. Comparison of measured cross-section ratio $A_{S,obs} / A_{obs}$ and A_S^* / A considering the transition effect for partially threaded bolts obtained by FEA

	ISO 4014 M8×50-5.6	ISO 4014 M8×50-8.8	ISO 4014 M16×90-8.8	ISO 4014 M16×90-8.8-tzn	ISO 4014 M16×90-10.9	EN 14399-4 M16×85-10.9-tzn
$A_{S,obs} / A_{obs}$	0.715	0.723	0.746	0.731	0.776	0.767
$F_t / F_{t,max} = A_S^* / A$	0.768	0.768	0.774	0.804	0.786	0.863

5 DESIGN PROPOSAL AND STATISTICAL EVALUATION

As a conclusion of the experimental results a new design approach for the interaction resistance of lockbolt systems is proposed, see Table 6. Considering the tension resistance of the shear cross-section in the test evaluation leads to a common arrangement of the results in the interaction diagrams, so that this is adopted in the design approach. The arrangement of threaded and unthreaded specimens, bolts and lockbolt systems shows no significant differences, which indicates a comparable load-bearing behaviour under combined tensile and shear loading and is confirmed by numerical investigations. In order to enable a harmonised design of connections with bolts and lockbolt systems, the design approach for carbon-steel bolts from Stranghoner/Abraham (13), see Eq. (4) and Eq. (5) is modified and transferred to lockbolt systems. Due to the different failure mechanism under tensile loading, the tensile resistance of the shear cross-section is independent from the tension resistance for collar stripping and must be calculated separately.

Table 6. Design proposal for interaction verification of lockbolt systems

Grooves are included in shear plane

$$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,A_S,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} \leq 1 \quad (14)$$

$$F_{t,Rd,A_S} = f_{ub} \cdot A_S / \gamma_{M2} \quad (15)$$

(A_S is the tensile stress area of the lockbolt)

Grooves are not included in shear plane

$$\left(\frac{F_{v,Ed}}{F_{v,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} + \left(\frac{F_{t,Ed}}{F_{t,A,Rd}}\right)^{1.7} \leq 1 \quad (16)$$

$$F_{t,Rd,A} = f_{ub} \cdot A / \gamma_{M2} \quad (17)$$

(A is the gross cross-section of the lockbolt)

Fig. 7 r_e - r_t -plot for proposed interaction approach with $\alpha_{v,obs}$

When developing a resistance function on the basis of experimental investigations, EN 1990 (23) requires a statistical evaluation in accordance with the procedure described in Annex D.8, explained in detail in (24) and (25), see also (26). Only test results for interaction failure in the shear plane are considered to evaluate the interaction approach. Results for collar stripping and single shearing ($\varphi = 90^\circ$) are not considered. In order to avoid mixing with the reliability from the shear coefficient α_v and in order to explain the actual interaction between tension and shear resistance, the statistical evaluation was initially carried out with the experimentally observed shear coefficient $\alpha_{v,obs}$. In addition, the nominal shear coefficient $\alpha_v = 0.55$ from DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4) was taken into account. The coefficients of variation of the basic variables f_{ub} and A or A_S are assumed as $V_{f_{ub}} = 7\%$ and $V_{A,A_S} = 1\%$ according to (24). Since the material strength is defined as a nominal value, the modified partial safety factor γ_{M}^* must be determined with the characteristic value of f_{ub} taking into account the fractile factor $k_{f_{ub}} = 2.0$ (24). Due to the large number of tests, the fractile factors are generally $k_n = 1.64$ and $k_{d,n} = 3.04$. The results of the statistical evaluation are presented in Table 7.

The theoretical value r_t is determined by the resistance function with the measured basic values of each test specimen and is compared with each experimental result r_e . The scattering of the

experimental and the theoretical value is described by the mean value correction b . An accurate and complete function would lead to $b = 1.0$, which is the aim. For a sufficient resistance model $b > 0.9$ is required. In German National Annex of DIN EN 1993-1-8 (27), the partial safety factor for the bolts resistance is given by $\gamma_{M2} = 1.25$. For the proposed interaction approach with both the observed and nominal shear coefficient, the statistical evaluation leads to $\gamma_M^* \leq 1.25$. As expected, considering the nominal shear coefficient results in increasing safeness respectively in decreasing γ_M^* . For that reason, the statistical evaluation of the common interaction approaches is carried out with $\alpha_{v,obs}$, to allow a better comparison. Since DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4) and EN/prEN 1993-1-8 (6; 8) do not consider the tension resistance of the shear cross-section, the resistance of collar stripping is taken into account. The results of statistical evaluation in Table 7 show a conservative design using the linear interaction models. For the quadratic interaction approach from DIN 18800-1 (10) the mean value correction b is close to the limit of being a sufficient resistance model and the partial safety factor exceeds 1.25.

Table 7. Statistical evaluation of interaction approaches applied to lockbolt systems

Interaction approach	b	V_δ	k_c	γ_M^*
Proposal for lockbolt systems ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	0.9541	0.0534	1.0053	1.19
Proposal for lockbolt systems ($\alpha = 0.55$)	1.0066	0.0705	1.0250	1.17
DVS-EFB 3435-2 (4) ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	1.3428	0.1195	1.0976	0.99
EN/prEN 1993-1-8 (6; 8) ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	1.1643	0.0886	1.0495	1.06
Može (9) ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	1.0607	0.0797	1.0372	1.14
Renner/Lange (12) ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	0.9937	0.0521	1.0039	1.14
DIN 18800-1 (10) ($\alpha_{v,obs}$)	0.9135	0.0599	1.0124	1.26

6 SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

Due to the comparable load bearing behaviour of bolting assemblies and lockbolt systems, for many load cases the design rules for lockbolt systems are adopted from bolting assemblies and modified if necessary. The verification of the load bearing capacity for lockbolts systems under combined tension and shear loading according to the linear interaction approach of DVS-EFB 3435-2 leads to a conservative design compared to the interaction approaches of standards and new proposals for bolted connections. Systematic experimental studies on the interaction load-bearing capacity of tensile test pieces, bolting assemblies and different types of lockbolt systems made from carbon steel were carried out and allow the comparison to common interaction models. The test evaluation shows that considering the correct resistances for the tension load component and the shear load component in the shear plane enables a suitable description of the interaction load bearing behaviour, independent from the failure mechanism for single tension loading. This can be seen by the common placement of the test results from different specimen types in the interaction diagram. Furthermore, the interaction load-bearing capacity of partially threaded bolts and lockbolt systems is still limited by the single tension resistance for the failure of the free loaded thread or the collar stripping outside of the shear plane. In consequence, the interaction approaches of EN 1993-1-8 and DVS-EFB 3435-2 do not generally represent the interaction load bearing behaviour. As they describe the interaction resistance by the interaction between the single tension and single shear resistances, the load bearing behaviour under combined tension and shear loading in the shear plane is not displayed for partially threaded bolts and lockbolt systems. Based on the findings on the interaction load bearing behaviour a new interaction approach for lockbolt systems is proposed and is verified by statistical evaluation. This interaction approach enables both a safe and an economical design of connection with lockbolt systems and will be part of the revision of technical bulletin EFB 3435-2.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The research project (No 20954 BR) of the European Research Association for Sheet Metal Working (EFB) has been funded within the program of Industrial Collective Research (IGF) of the German Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action on the basis of a decision by the German Bundestag. The authors would like to thank the sponsors and the participating companies for their support.

7 REFERENCES

1. **ISO 898-1:2013-05**. Mechanical properties of fasteners made of carbon steel and alloy steel - Part 1: Bolts, screws and studs with specified property classes - Coarse thread and fine pitch thread.
2. **DVS-EFB 3435-1:2021-10**. Lockbolt systems.
3. **Glienke, Ralf, et al.** Joints with lockbolts in steel structures – Part 1: Lockbolt technology. *Steel Construction*. 2020, 13, pp. 120-127.
4. **DVS-EFB 3435-2:2016-05**. Lockbolt systems - calculation of connections according to Eurocode 3 and VDI 2230-Part 1.
5. **Gilenke, Ralf, et al.** Joints with lockbolts in steel structures – Part 2: Design. *Steel Construction*. 2020, 13.
6. **EN 1993-1-8:2010-12**. Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints.
7. **Holch, Alexander**. *Tragverhalten kombiniert beanspruchter Verbindungen mit Schließringbolzensystemen*. 2023. IGF-Projekt 20954BR.
8. **prEN 1993-1-8:2021**. Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures – Part 1-8: Design of joints.
9. **Može, Primož**. Bolts in tension and shear - Background Document for Project Team SC3.T2 in the Frame of Revision of EN 1993–1-. Ljubljana : s.n., 2017.
10. **DIN 18800-1**. Steel structures - Part 1: Design and construction.
11. **Knobloch, Manfred and Schmidt, Herbert**. *Tragfähigkeit und Tragverhalten stahlbauüblicher Schrauben unter reiner Scherbeanspruchung und unter kombinierter Scher- Zugbeanspruchung*. 1987. Forschungsberichte aus dem Fachbereich Bauwesen 41.
12. **Renner, Anja und Lange, Jörg**. Zum Tragverhalten und zur Bemessung von Schrauben unter kombinierter Zug-Abscher-Belastung. *Stahlbau*. 2019, 4, pp. 324-330.
13. **Stranghöner, Natalie, Abraham, Christoph und Ehrhard, Lukas**. New design approaches for tension, shear and interaction resistance of carbon steel bolts. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 2024, 212.
14. **Chesson, Eugene Jr., Faustino, N. L. und Munse, W. H.** High-Strength Bolts Subjected to Tension and Shear. *Journal of the Structural Division, Vol. 91, Issue 5*. 1965.
15. **Dörre, Maik, et al.** Bewertung des Scherfestigkeitsverhältnisses für Schrauben festgelegter Festigkeitsklassen. 2019, Bde. pp. 382-404.
16. **ISO 4017:2022-10**. Fasteners - Hexagon head screws - Product grades A and B.
17. **ISO 4014:2022-10**. Fasteners - Hexagon head bolts - Product grades A and B.
18. **DIN 50125:2022-08**. Testing of metallic materials - Tensile test pieces.
19. **EN 14399-4:2015-04**. High-strength structural bolting assemblies for preloading - Part 4: System HV - Hexagon bolt and nut assemblies.
20. **ISO 6507-1:2024-01**. Metallic materials - Vickers hardness test - Part 1: Test method.
21. **ISO 18265:2014-02**. Metallic materials - Conversion of hardness values.
22. **Schneider, Wilhelm und Thomala, Wolfgang**. Hinweise zur Anwendung des Spannungsquerschnitts von Schraubengewinden. *VDI-Zeitung*. 1984, 126, pp. 84-91.
23. **EN 1990:2021-10**. Basis of structural design.
24. **Bijlaard, F., Sedlacek, G. und Stark, J.** *Procedure for the determination of design resistance from tests - Background report to Eurocode 3 "Common unified rules for Steelstructures"*. 1988. TNO-rapport BI-87-112.
25. **Gulvanessian, Haig, Calgaro, Jean-Armand und Holický, Milan**. Designers' Guide to Eurocode: Basis of structural design - EN 1990, Second edition. *ICE Publishing*. 2012.
26. **Može, Primož**. Statistical evaluation of bearing resistance and related strength functions for bolted connection. *Journal of Constructional Steel Research*. 2020, 171.
27. **DIN EN 1993-1-8/NA:2020-11**. National Annex - Nationally determined parameters - Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-8: Design of joints.